

Analytical Modeling of Internal Quantum Efficiency of CIGS Solar Cell

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ABSTRACT

In this paper an analytical model for the internal quantum efficiency is developed for the CIGS based Solar Cell. In doing so a uniform electric field has been assumed in the depletion region. The developed model shows that this proposed model can provide a better physical insight for Internal Quantum Efficiency for CIGS solar cells.

KEY WORDS: Thin film Solar Cell, Heterojunction Cells, CIGS, Internal Quantum Efficiency, Absorption Coefficient.

1. INTRODUCTION

The second-generation thin film solar cells are increasingly promising for their cheaper production and better efficiency. $CuIn_{1-x}Ga_xSe_2$ (CIGS) based cell is one of the most potential photoconductors for thin film solar cells because of its excellent efficiency [1]. The subscript x represents the mole fraction. The CIGS based solar cells have a substrate device structure of grid /ZnO /CdS /CIGS/Mo/glass [2][3]. The CIGS based cells are p-n heterojunction cells, where a very thin layer (50 μ m) of CdS acts as a highly doped n-layer and CIGS layer acts as lightly doped p-type absorber layer [4]. The thickness of the p-layer is 3000 μ m. The voltage dependent charge collection in the depleted absorber layer is the dominant charge collection mechanisms in thin film solar cells [3][5].

Internal Quantum Efficiency η is one of the most important factors of a solar cell because the efficiency of the solar cells is still limited; for example, commercial panels and terrestrial energy conversion, the efficiency is approximately 10% and up to 24% respectively [6]. The physics can be described by modeling the η accurately. So, various researchers have been working on the accurate modeling of η considering various effects. For CIGS based solar cells, Gloeckler [7] describes the device physics. Johansson [8] developed a numerical model of CIGS cell based on one diode model, whereas Gloeckler [9] derived a numerical model using AMPS Modeling. But these works did not develop an analytical model of η for CIGS solar cells.

In this work, an analytical model of η is developed for CIGS based solar cells and also observed the

change of η with changing in lifetime and doping concentration.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Basic Equations

The hole current density, J_p within the depletion region is given as:

$$J_p = qp(x)\mu_p(x)E_p(x) - qD_p(x)\frac{dp(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where μ_p and D_p are hole mobility and hole diffusivity respectively. The Current continuity equation is given by :

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -q(R - G) \quad (2)$$

The electron current density, J_n within the depletion region is given as:

$$J_n = qn(x)\mu_n(x)E_n(x) + qD_n(x)\frac{dn(x)}{dx} \quad (3)$$

where μ_n and D_n are electron mobility and electron diffusivity respectively. The Current continuity equation is given by :

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q(R - G) \quad (4)$$

R-G is the net recombination rate.

2.2 Physical Models

2.2.1 Recombination-Generation

As we consider low doping, only SRH recombination will be present in our model. Therefore, from current continuity equation we get

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -q\frac{P}{\tau_p} + q\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha x} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q\frac{n}{\tau_n} - q\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha x} \quad (6)$$

2.3 Boundary Conditions

Boundary condition for depletion region are given as below:

1. for electrons at $x = W_E + W_d$;

$$n(W_E + W_d) = \frac{n_i^2}{N_A} \quad (7)$$

2. for holes at $x = W_E$;

$$P(W_E) = \frac{n_i^2}{N_D} \quad (8)$$

2.4 Model Derivation

1. The hole current equation (1) can be rearranged as

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = q\mu_p E_p \frac{dp}{dx} \quad (9)$$

Using equation (9) and equation (5) we will get a first order differential equation of $p(x)$ as follows:

$$\frac{dp}{dx} + \frac{p}{\tau_p \mu_p E_p} = \frac{-\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha x}}{\mu_p E_p} \quad (10)$$

Now solving this first order differential equation we get

$$P(x) = C_p e^{-\frac{x}{\tau_p \mu_p E_p}} - \frac{G_0}{\mu_p E_p} e^{-\alpha x} \quad (11)$$

Here, C_p is constant.

Now using boundary condition from equation (7) we get the value of C_p and this is:

$$C_p = \left(\frac{n_i^2}{N_d} + \frac{F_0}{\mu_p E_p} e^{-\alpha W_E} \right) e^{\frac{W_E}{\tau_p \mu_p E_p}} \quad (12)$$

Now, substituting this value of C_p in equation (11) we get the value of $p(x)$ and then from equation (1) we get the value of $J_p(x)$.

2. The electron current equation (3) can be rearranged as

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q\mu_n E_n \frac{dn}{dx} \quad (13)$$

Using equation (13) and equation (6) we will get a first order differential equation of $n(x)$ as follows:

$$\frac{dn}{dx} - \frac{n}{\tau_n \mu_n E_n} = \frac{-\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha x}}{\mu_n E_n} \quad (14)$$

Now solving this first order differential equation we get

$$n(x) = C_n e^{\frac{x}{\tau_n \mu_n E_n}} + \frac{G_0}{\mu_n E_n} e^{-\alpha x} \quad (15)$$

Here, C_n is constant.

Now using boundary condition from equation (8) we get the value of C_n and this is:

$$C_n = \left(\frac{n_i^2}{N_A} - \frac{G_0}{\mu_n E_n} e^{-\alpha(W_E+W_d)} \right) e^{\frac{-(W_E+W_d)}{\tau_n \mu_n E_n}} \quad (16)$$

Now, substituting this value of C_n in equation (15) we get the value of $n(x)$ and then from equation (3) we get value of $J_n(x)$.

3. Now the total current is:

$$J_{tot}(x) = J_p(x) + J_n(x) \quad (17)$$

Now internal quantum efficiency is given by,

$$\eta = \frac{J_{tot}}{J_G} \quad (18)$$

where

$$J_G = q \int G_0 \left(1 - e^{-\alpha(W_E+W_d+W_b)} \right) \quad (19)$$

3. RESULTS

The results for the proposed model are presented and analyzed in this section. The base width of the CIGS cell is chosen as 3000 μ m. Fig. (1) shows that left side of the figure is the base region while right side is the emitter and the middle region is the depletion region. This figure shows that η is the highest in the depletion region where η in the base side is low because of the low absorption and the emitter side is for the surface recombination. Fig. (2) and Fig. (3) show the variations on η with the variation of lifetimes. From Fig. (2), it is seen that η slightly changes when the lifetime of electrons changes because of the increase in carrier generation. The effect of variation of lifetime of holes on the internal quantum efficiency is plotted in Fig. (3). Keeping τ_n constant and increasing τ_p , the Internal Quantum Efficiency increases because carrier generation increases with the increasing τ_p . Comparing this two figures (2) and (3), hole transport is dominant. Fig. (4) showing the effect of changing the doping concentration, N_a on the Internal Quantum Efficiency. If we increase the doping concentration, N_a while keeping N_d constant, then the Internal Quantum Efficiency decreases because with the increasing N_a , the width of the depletion region decreases. For this, the generation in the depletion region also decreases. So, η decreases.

Figure 1: The change of internal quantum efficiency with respect to absorption coefficient in the depletion region and $N_d = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_a = 2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $S = 10^7 \text{ cms}^{-1}$.

Figure 2: The change of internal quantum efficiency with respect to absorption coefficient in the depletion region with change in the life time of electron, where, $\tau_p = 10^{-10} \text{ s}$, $S = 10^7 \text{ cms}^{-1}$, $N_a = 2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_d = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

4. Conclusion

In this work, an analytical model of Internal Quantum Efficiency for Cigs based solar cells has been derived considering uniform field in the depletion region. The results of the developed model points out that hole transport is dominant and if doping concentration (N_a) increase, then internal quantum efficiency decreases.

Figure 3: The change of internal quantum efficiency with respect to absorption coefficient in the depletion region with change in the life time of hole, where, $\tau_n = 10^{-6} \text{ s}$, $S = 10^7 \text{ cms}^{-1}$, $N_a = 2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_d = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 4: The change of internal quantum efficiency with respect to absorption coefficient in the depletion region with change in the doping concentration (N_a), where, $\tau_p = 10^{-10} \text{ s}$, $\tau_n = 10^{-6} \text{ s}$, $S = 10^7 \text{ cms}^{-1}$, $N_d = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

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